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Fishery, Earth Observation, Modelling and Prediction (FJOMP)

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A Pilot Study

by

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REPORT

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1 Introduction and Objectives

1.1 Project Background

About 30 years after the start of the satellite Earth Observation (EO) era, we are facing a situation with increased and improved availability of satellite Earth observation data. Some of the early EO sensors are still maintained with compatible sensor systems and the tendency among the world-wide Space Agencies is that it is essential to obtain and maintain comparable EO time series over periods of decades. Mapping of marine environmental phenomenon such as: sea surface temperature (SST), ocean topography, sea ice concentration and extent, ocean colour, etc. will be provided by at least two to three different satellite systems over at least the next five years period. Individually each of these satellite sensors will provide important information for both research and operational monitoring. However, regular, consistent synergetic and integrated use of these data with other observations and numerical prediction model tools are needed to fully exploit the available information about our environment, as suggested in Figure 1.

The longer the time series of consistent EO data are, the more suitable they become for trend and other statistical analysis in conjunction with other information sources such as fish stock assessments. The longest consistent EO time series over oceans are about 20 years (passive microwave mapping of sea ice, and infrared sensing of SST by AVHRR). In addition time series of ocean topography (currents) have been regularly obtained from satellite altimetry during the last 10-15 years. Regular long time series of ocean colour data, on the other hand, is lacking with a large gap of more than 12 years between the CZCS and the SeaWiFS sensors.

Long time series of (30-50 years) of information from the fisheries research and management are available for major parts of the Norwegian marine and coastal areas. The use of this information in conjunction with the EO data will enable us to search for relations between the inter-annual variation in the marine physical environment and the fish stock assessment, catch statistics and other information currently used within the fisheries management.

The scope of this report is to identify the most relevant and appropriate EO data and their existing data products, which shall be systematically analysed in combination with the regularly used information from the Norwegian fisheries research and management.

1.2 The relations between physical climate and fish stock variability

For several decades, the main aims of fishery research and management have been to understand and explain the great variability in survival from egg to mature fish. In studies of the ecology of the ocean, and especially in fishery biology, a common assumption is that the

physical climate has a strong influence on population dynamics (e.g. recruitment success, and migration pattern). It has however, often been difficult to demonstrate such relations directly.

Figure 1: A schematic overview of the various elements involved in a integrated application of in situ and EO data and numerical models for the applications to fisheries research and management.

This may be because the impact mechanisms and relations are complex while the investigations often consider only one single physical parameter at a given time (i.e. temperature), which is not necessarily the only or main steering ecological factor.

During the last 20 years we have observed large variability in the oceans in high latitude northern areas. Low temperature, low salinity and weak wind dominated the end of the 1970s - the so called “The Great Salinity Anomaly” (Dickson et al. 1988) - while extremely mild winters and strong westerly winds were the rule during the first half of the 1990s. This was associated with changes in the transport and composition of Atlantic Water (AW) and water from the Arctic Ocean. It was also coupled to the variation in the large-scale atmospheric climate such as given by the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) index, causing anomalies of the forcing field such as air-sea heat exchange, wind speed, and wind direction and in turn the mass and heat fluxes of AW. Such variations in the ocean and in the atmosphere have assumingly had large effects on the recruitment, growth and migration on several of the most important fish stocks.

There is no doubt that correlation between biological and physical variability related to such climatic variations exists on a time scale of 5-10 years. However, significant biological variability is often observed from one year to the next. To understand which (of several partly

correlated) climatic factors that are of vital importance for biology, one must be able to quantify the possible connections from year to year. In this respect it is vital to have information on the most important parameters, which directly or indirectly effects the fish stocks. For this reason the project will investigate how contribution from long term satellite Earth Observation monitoring may help and advice fishery research and management.

A very clear relation between fisheries and ocean physics is demonstrated in Figure 2. A half-year highly correlated time delay is observed in the variation of the catches of herring during the summer period and the changes in the modelled water fluxes in to the North Sea during the earlier winter season of the same year. This demonstrates a very close link between the influx of relatively warm and nutrient rich Atlantic Water to the northern North Sea during winter and the catches of herring approximately half a year later. The hypothesis for this relation is that the Atlantic Water opens a "gateway" to the North Sea for the herring on its annual search for food after spawning west of the British Isles, then migrating into the North Sea.

Horse mackerel and winter volume fluxes

Figure 2: The variation of the catches of horse mackerel in the North Sea from 1976 to 1998 and the modelled flux of warm Atlantic water inflow during winter to the North Sea (after Iversen, 1998).

1.3 The Objectives

The objective of this report is to define an approach for an integrated project (the main project) on Fishery, Earth Observation, Modelling and Prediction (FJOMP). In the main project, systematic investigations of selected satellite EO data together with other information (*in situ* data, catch statistics etc.) and numerical models will be carried out in order to search for new knowledge on the relations between the fish stocks and the climatic environmental variability. Such knowledge may in turn improve fishery research and management.

The objectives of the main project are:

1. To improve the understanding of the connection between variations in ocean climate on the regional-scale and the ecology of importance to fish stocks on the other. The transport of nutrients, larvae and eggs by ocean currents, as well as the temperature and stability of the water are considered to be important variables in this context.
2. To select suitable EO based data and parameters for description of water temperature, currents, stability, turbulence, light conditions and biology, for the use of these as input into models for computing fish stocks size, recruitment, growth and migration.

1.4 Geographical area of interest to Norwegian Fisheries Authority.

The main areas of interest to the Norwegian fisheries research and management are the Barents Sea, the Nordic Seas (Norwegian, Iceland and Greenland Seas), the North Sea, and waters west of the British Isles. However, to investigate the ocean climate in these waters, the conditions further west and south (e.g. the North Atlantic Current and Gulf Stream), and also within the Arctic Ocean are highly relevant and must be taken into account.

Figure 3 shows the geographic distribution of some of the most important commercial species such as cod, herring and capelin. Each of the species consists of two or more populations, which are affected differently by climate due to their different areas of spawning, drift and migration, and their different food sources. In this game of eating or being eaten, cannibalism sometimes play an important role in the population dynamics.

Figure 3: The geographic distribution of some main species (cod, herring and capelin) for the Norwegian fisheries (after Muus, 1992).

2 Data sources and fish stock models

The two prime categories of data sources are: 1) selected satellite EO data of relevance to the key parameters of the physical and partly biological marine environment, and 2) the *in situ* fish stock and other marine physical information currently in use by the Norwegian fishery research and management authorities. These data will be subject to a comprehensive statistical analysis and methods for integration into existing fish stock assessment models will be investigated, developed and implemented.

2.1 Description and availability of Relevant Earth Observation Data

For analysis of climate and environment in relation to recruitment, growth and migration of fish stock, we need long time series of consistent data sets with a calibration that does not change unpredictably during the period. However, if the sensor shows degradation over time (as was the case for e.g. the CZCS instrument), or is affected by atmospheric changes (as e.g. volcanic eruptions did for the AVHRR instrument) it is necessary to correct for these error sources.

As many of the most interesting variations to be observed in the context of FJOMP are on a decadal time scale of typically 5 -10 years, the data series should preferably exceed 10 years.

Sufficiently long time series of consistent calibrated and relevant EO-data are available from the following two US series of satellites:

- 1) the TIROS/NOAA-satellites with their optical (visual and infrared) sensitive Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) instrument, and
- 2) the US NIMBUS-7 and DMSP-satellites with their passive microwave instruments Scanning Multi-frequency Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) and Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I), respectively.

These instruments have global daily coverage at high latitudes. The resulting data sets:

- a) Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and
- b) Sea ice concentration, extent and ice edge location,

are both recommended for use within FJOMP and are described in detail below.

In addition, several other EO-data sets of shorter duration or with interrupted operation are also available. These includes measurements by satellite radar altimeter (RA) of sea surface topography in order to derive the ocean current variations, and measurement of ocean colour and chlorophyll by visual radiometer, which also are recommended for use within FJOMP, which are addressed further below.

2.1.1 Description of AVHRR based Sea Surface Temperature (SST)

For ocean fisheries, the most relevant physical ocean parameter from the AVHRR instruments is the sea surface temperature (SST). However, AVHRR signals do not penetrate clouds, severely limiting its regular use for surface temperature measurements in Norwegian waters. Efficient cloud screening and measurement averaging over longer periods are therefore necessary to obtain useful information in frequently cloud covered ocean areas.

The use of so-called "split-channel" (the 10 -12 μ spectral window split into two channels, no. 4 and no. 5) algorithms is commonly used for making atmospheric corrections to the derived sea surface temperature. The standard product used by NOAA is called Multi-Channel Sea Surface Temperature (MCSST). A continuous time series of corrected SST data is available by using the satellites NOAA-7, NOAA-9, NOAA-11 and NOAA-14, spanning the years from 1981 to the present. Internal channel calibration close to $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{K}$ is available for these satellites. The absolute accuracy in the atmosphere-corrected MCSST is near $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{K}$ (globally, and somewhat better locally and at high latitudes). Internal instrument calibration and negligible drift ensure the stability of the measurements. Satellite swath data are available in 1 km resolution, but for our purpose the data are binned to a coarser grid, typically 10–50 km.

Atmospheric correction coefficients are tuned at NOAA shortly after launch of each new satellite. Large volcanic eruptions, such as the Mount Pinatubo eruption in 1991, may change the atmospheric correction applied to the AVHRR data in periods. The data sets recommended for FJOMP have been subjected to modifications designed to handle such events.

Distinction between Ascending and Descending pass data is often made, due to systematic differences in the algorithm and quality of day and night data, the night data being generally considered as the most accurate (less effect of the skin-temperature). A list of TIROS -NOAA satellites carrying AVHRR are given in Table 1.

Table 1. TIROS -NOAA satellites carrying AVHRR sensors

Satellite	Operation dates	Split-channel
TIROS-N	Oct. 78 -Jan. 80	No
NOAA-6	Jun. 79 -Mar. 83	No
NOAA-7	Aug. 81 - Feb. 85	Yes
NOAA-8	May. 83 -Oct. 85	No
NOAA-9	Feb. 85 - Nov. 88	Yes
NOAA-10	Nov. 86 - Sep. 91	No
NOAA-11	Nov. 88 - Apr. 95	Yes
NOAA-12	Sep. 91 - present	Yes
NOAA-14	Dec. 94 - present	Yes

2.1.2 Availability of AVHRR Sea Surface Temperature data

Weekly averaged data sets between November 1981 and August 1999 for both Ascending (day-time) and Descending (night-time) orbits, are available on equal-angle latitude-longitude grids of 18 km squares at equator. These data are provided by the NASA Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PO.DAAC) at Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) in Pasadena, CA (http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/order/order_avhrr.html). Several application areas are listed, including climate studies and fishery research.

As part of the ongoing "AVHRR Oceans Pathfinder" project, JPL is tasked with reprocessing AVHRR to produce an accurate SST database especially suited for global climate studies. New processing procedures are used to improve the calibration accuracy and the number of valid retrievals (based on a quality flag). An example of the data coverage for 8 days averages are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Global map of the spatial coverage of the land and cloud masked PODAAC SST data during eight days.

Daily and Monthly sets of quality controlled (named "best") SST Pathfinder data between January 1985 and July 1999 for both daytime (ascending) and night time (descending) orbits, are available from JPL on three equal-angle latitude-longitude grids:

- 9 km squares at equator,
- 18 km squares at equator,
- 54 km squares at equator,

Using the Pathfinder SST data set described above, E. Dombrowsky at CLS ARGOS in Toulouse (working with the MAST-III "DIADEM" project, where The Nansen Center is a partner), has computed an SST database for use as input to climate models consisting of 11-day average night pass values on a 28km squares grid. The period covered is October 1992 – December 1996.

The higher level aggregated database for SST to be used in FJOMP is generally available and prepared to a level for use with only minor adjustments and data extraction of the actual regions to be analysed.

2.1.3 Passive microwave Sea ice concentration and Ice edge

The most relevant parameter for fisheries applications from the SMMR and SSMI instruments is the ice edge position, which can be estimated on a daily basis. Also sea ice concentration and extent are available, as well as discrimination between First-year and Multi-year ice during the winter season (see Figure 5). The algorithms used to combine 2-4 of the available channels to ice concentration are almost insensitive to atmospheric moisture, the only exception being heavy rain. The SSMI instruments used are very similar on all the DMSP satellites and have internal calibration to about $\pm 1^\circ\text{K}$. Overlapping periods of measurement have been used to improve the calibration between satellites (Bjørge et.al, 1997 and Cavalieri et.al, 1999). The accuracy of the ice concentration is estimated to be about $\pm 5\%$. Using the highest frequency channel on SSMI, ice concentration resolution of about 20km is possible, but the standard algorithms compute the concentration to about 50km resolution.

A list of the passive microwave satellites is given in Table 2.

Table 2. US satellites carrying a passive microwave imaging radiometer.

Satellite	Operation dates	Used in sea ice database
NIMBUS-7	Oct. 78 - Aug. 87	Yes
DMSP F-8	June, 87 - Dec. 91	Yes
DMSP F-10	Dec. 90 - 94	
DMSP F-11	Nov. 91 - Sep. 95	Yes
DMSP F-12	Aug. 94 - 97	
DMSP F-13	Mar. 95 - present	Yes
DMSP F-14	1997 - present	
DMSP F-15	1998 - present	

As these satellites are operated in pairs, each having a daily global coverage, only a subset is needed for generating a continuous data set of ice concentration, as noted in the last column.

2.1.4 Availability of Sea ice concentration from Passive microwave sensors

Daily and Monthly mean Sea ice concentration values, using the "NASA Team" algorithm, computed between October 1978 and December 1996 are available at NERSC, acquired from the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) in Colorado, on a 25 km polar projection grid.

Monthly mean sea ice concentration values, using the "NORSEX" algorithm (Svendsen et al, 1983), computed by the Nansen Centers in Bergen and St. Petersburg is also available. The period covered is January 1979 – December 1998, also on a 25km polar projection grid (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. An example of the sea ice information retrieved from passive microwave EO data. These time series of information available from 1978 to present can be analysed for the various sea ice parameters as well as the different regions of the Arctic in order to be used in the FJOMP main project. Courtesy NERSC.

The routines used for processing of the EO data are operational and further updates of the times series of information as well as regional data extraction are available at the Nansen Center.

2.1.5 Radar Altimetry and Ocean Current Variability information

In relation to fisheries, the most relevant quantity provided by radar altimetry in the surface geostrophic currents. Satellite radar altimetry (RA) measures the range from the satellite to the sea surface with an accuracy at a few centimetres level. From these altitude measurements, the ocean topography can be computed along a track beneath the satellite, resulting in a regular (more or less closely spaced) global pattern of lines of sea-surface height with a repeat-period of typically 10–35 days. Using this surface-height information, one can derive and accurately monitor variations in the geostrophic ocean currents and the tides, the variables being integrated for various time and spatial length scales. Variation in temperature and salinity integrated over the water depth (water density variations) will also influence the sea-surface height and must be accounted for when the variation of the geostrophic ocean currents is computed. In addition to range measurement, the RA signal can also be used to measure significant wave height and wind speed.

Changes in geostrophic ocean surface currents introduce changes of the sea surface height by up to a meter over a scale of typically one hundred kilometer (i.e. for the Gulf Stream). Satellite radar altimeters have supplied continuous world wide observations and increased our knowledge of the ocean circulation since the early altimeter on Seasat in 1978.

Ocean surface topography measurements by satellite radar altimeters represent a relatively low-cost EO data source for regular monitoring of ocean currents variability. Recent improvements in orbit determinations and geoid modelling, satellite orbit tracking, and the availability of overlapping coverage from more than one RA satellite sensor, have made available high quality ocean circulation information from altimeter data.

Higher level products derived from altimeters includes the root-mean-square of sea level variability, and the eddy kinetic energy. These variables show areas of low and high ocean currents variability. The circulation is generally associated with ocean currents represented by meso-scale eddies and rings. Other ocean products derived from RA include sea level variations and cross track velocity fields for selected track segments, time series of sea level at selected positions, gridded sea level and velocity fields, and spatial and temporal statistics on inter-annual or seasonal time scales of the ocean circulation pattern.

Evensen et al., (1999) demonstrates the usefulness of the radar altimeter measurements of dynamic topography and ocean circulation from ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites assimilated in an isopycnal numerical ocean model (based on the MICOM code) for North Atlantic. The result of assimilation of RA data in the model clearly improves its prediction performances.

It is therefore recommend to include the satellite radar altimetry in the studies of the relationship between ocean climate in the North Atlantic/Nordic Seas and fishery statistics in the FJOMP main project.

2.1.6 Availability of Radar Altimeter Data Products

Starting with the GEOS-3 mission in 1975 the RA sensors has been among the priority EO instruments for ocean monitoring. The list of the available and the near future planned RA sensors are given in Table 3.

Since the beginning of this decade (August 1991) several altimetry satellite missions (ERS-1, ERS-2, T/P) have been flying simultaneously. This will continue in the near future with the planned US Geosat follow-on, the European Envisat and US/French Jason missions. As such we can envision 15 years of continuous altimetric satellite missions.

Table 3. Overview of the past and future RA missions.

Mission	Launch	Completed
GEOS-3	1975	1978
Seasat	1978	1978
Geosat	1985	1989
ERS-1	1991	1996
Topex/Poseidon	1992	Operational
ERS-2	1995	Operational
Geosat Follow-on	1999	Not working
Jason	2000	-
ENVISAT	2001	-
Oceansat II	2002	-

As a part of the CEO OPERALT project merged data from ERS and Topex/Poseidon for the period October 1992 – October 1998 have been produced, with the general objective of extracting ocean current data of interest for users in the offshore industry. A full analysis of the geostrophic current variability in the Norwegian Sea is made, using an optimal satellite altimeter data set with regard to both error level and resolution. A 7-year data set, on a 10km grid and with 10 days averaging, have been produced at NERSC. The data set contain: 1) sea level anomaly, 2) current velocity anomaly, 3) eddy kinetic energy (see Figure 6). It is recommended for inclusion in FJOMP main project.

Figure 6. Eddy Kinetic Energy distribution averaged for the months January to March in the years 1993-98. The red and yellow colours represents the high energy areas associated with the inflow of Atlantic water. Courtesy: CLS.

2.1.7 Other relevant EO data with shorter or interrupted availability

In relation to the fisheries the ocean colour sensors may be the EO sensors measuring parameters directly related to the marine living resources. Through measurements of ocean colour from EO sensors one can estimate the marine phytoplankton (algae) concentration as well as the marine primary production. Ocean colour and primary productivity have been measured from the satellite/instrument NIMBUS-7 Coastal Zone Colour Scanner (CZCS) from 1978 to 1986, and by Orbview-2 Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS) since 1997. The instruments have comparable characteristics and data can be processed to water colour, and then by ratio techniques to phytoplankton (chlorophyll) concentration in the upper water layer. The atmosphere signal contribution is up to 80-90 %, and the atmospheric correction and processing is very important but complex, in particular for coastal waters. The CZCS sensor also had some serious calibration problems, which limited the period of reliable data. Cloud cover severely limits the amount of useful optical EO data in the majority of the areas of interest, but the potential for use in fish stock analysis is nevertheless significant. Inclusion in FJOMP is therefore recommended, even if the period of reliable EO data at present is short. Monthly averaged CZCS data for 8 years co-registered with MCSST data for 1981-86 on 18 km grid are available from JPL (product no.15) on CD ROM. SeaWiFS data and derived data products are available from NASA Goddard Space Flight Center at: <http://seawifs.gsfc.nasa.gov/SEAWIFS.html>. NERSC has also through other project activities NRT access to regional SeaWiFS data for the North Sea from the receiving station in Dundee and the UK processing service at CCMS-PML in Plymouth (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. An example of the SeaWiFS ocean colour data resolving the phytoplankton concentration (left) and the reflected light (right) in the North Sea, during an event of extensive Coccolithophorid bloom (bright area in right panel) along the coast of southern west-Norway. Courtesy: NERSC.

Sea surface temperature (SST) is also measured by several other EO sensor systems of shorter periods of operation. One of these is ERS Along-Track-Scanning-Radiometer (ATSR), in operation since 1991. The accuracy of the product is increased relative to AVHRR by inclusion of the "dual angle" method in the algorithm for atmospheric correction. It measures "skin temperature" as compared to MCSST "bulk temperature", the former is important for air-sea interaction studies. It also has a greater sensitivity, to enable low-contrast SST differences and fronts to be seen. None of these differences are considered of special importance for FJOMP. An ATSR-1 Data CD-ROM with monthly mean SST maps from July 91 to August 95 on a 54km grid with day and night values combined, is available from the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in England.

2.2 Availability of In-situ and Fish stock data

The Institute of Marine Research collects most of the *in situ* marine environmental data and also most of the fish stock data to be considered for use in this proposed investigation. Additional marine and fish stock data for areas outside the main Norwegian investigation areas can be obtained through the International Council for Exploration of the Seas (ICES).

With respect to the in-situ marine environmental data, the key activities, observation frequencies, parameters, and start year of regular observations are all given in Table 4. With respect to fisheries, Table 5 summarises the data sets available at the Institute of Marine Research and/or from ICES. In addition several time series from special surveys on young fish in the Barents Sea and coast of northern Norway has recently been produced in the national research project BASYS.

Table 4. Overview of the regularly obtained in situ observations from stations and cruises at IMR of relevance for use in FJOMP.

Activity	Observations/year	Parameters	Start year
Fixed Stations			
Hydrographic stations, coastal	26 - 40	T, S	1935
Thermographic service	100 coast, 50 North Sea	T, S	1936
Flødevigen Research Station	350, *50	T, S, *Ppl (harmful algae)	1924
Fjords: Rogaland - Finnmark	1 (Nov-Des)	T, S, N, O ₂	1975
Fjords: Skagerrak	1 (Oct), 12*	T, S, O ₂ * Oslofjord, T,S,N,O ₂	1920
Coastal monit., southern coast	12-24	T, S, N, O ₂ , Pm, Kl, Ppl, Zpl	1990
Station Mike - Norwegian Sea	60 (T/S)	T, S, N, Kl, Ppl, Zpl	1948
Fixed Sections			
Torungen - Hirtshals	11	T, S, O ₂ , N, Kl	1951
Hanstholm - Aberdeen	4 (Feb, April, June-July, *Nov)	T, S, *N, *Kl	1970
Oksø - Hanstholmen	4 (Feb, *April, June-July, *Nov)	T, S, *N, *Kl	1970
Utsira - Start Point	4 (Feb, April, June-July, *Nov)	T, S, *N, *Kl	1970
Feie - Shetland	4 (Feb, Apr, June-July, *Nov)	T, S, *N, *Kl	1970
Svinøy - NW	2 (Mar-Apr, July-Aug) *5-10 after 1995	T, S, *N, *Kl, *Ppl, *Zpl	1978
Gimsøy -NW	2 (Mar-Apr, July-Aug) *5-10 after 1995	T, S, *N, *Kl, *Ppl, *Zpl	1978
Fugløya - Bjørnøya	6 (Jan, Mar, Apr-May, June, Aug-Sept, Oct)	T, S, N, Kl, Zpl	1968
Bjørnøya -W	2 (March, Oct)	T, S	1958
Sørkapp -W	1 (Aug/Sept)	T, S	1978
Vardø -N	4 (Jan, Mar, June, Aug-Sept, Oct)	T, S, N, Kl, Zpl	1953
Sermøyene - N	2 (Jan-Feb, Aug-Sept)	T, S	1977
Regional coverage			
Barents Sea	4 (Jan-Feb, **June, *Aug - Sept)	T, S, *N, *Kl, *Zpl, **Flrv	1966
Barents Sea	Periodic observations	Contaminants, radioactivity, org. mat.	1991
Norwegian Sea (Central/Northern)	3 (May, July-Aug, Oct-Nov)	T, S, O ₂ , N, Kl, Zpl	1951
Norwegian Sea (Central/Northern)	Periodic observations	Contaminants and org. mat.	1994
Norwegian coast, North of 62°	2 (*Apr, Oct)	T, S, *Flrv,Zpl,*N	1981
North Sea/Skagerrak	4 (Jan, July, Oct, *Nov-Des)	T, S, *N, *Kl	1967
North Sea/Skagerrak	Periodic observations	Contaminants, radioactivity,	1991
Skagerrak - Jylland W	1 (April)	T, S, N,O ₂ , Kl, Ppl	1988
Lofoten	1 (March - April)	T, S	1951
Ireland - Shetland - Faroe Is.	2 (March-April, May-June)	T, S	1971
Svalbard - W	1 (Aug-Sept)	T, S	1981

T=temperature, S=salinity, O₂=oxygen, N=nutrients, Pm=particulate matter, Kl=chlorophyll-a, Ph=phytoplankton, Zpl=zooplankton, Flrv=fish larvae
* in column 2 refers to the selected parameters in column 3

Table 5: Summary of the fisheries related data sets available at the Institute of Marine Research and/or from ICES.

<i>North Sea</i>		
Total catch of demersal and pelagic fish	since	1988
Herring; spawning stock biomass (SSB) and catch at length pr. year-class	“	1960
Mackerel; -----“-----	“	1966
Horsemackerel; -----“-----	“	1983
Cod; Total stock, SSB, catch at length pr. year-class, recruits pr. year-class	“	1963
Saith; -----“-----	“	1972
Whiting; -----“-----	“	1960
Haddock; -----“-----	“	1963
<i>Nordic Sea/Norwegian coast</i>		
Total catch of demersal and pelagic fish	since	1988
Herring; catch at age pr. year class	“	1907
Herring; Total stock, SSB and catch at length pr. year-class, recruitment	“	1960
Blue Whiting; -----“-----	“	1980
Saith; -----“-----	“	1958
Greenland halibut-----“-----	“	1967
Redfish -----“-----	“	1965
<i>Barents Sea</i>		
Total catch of demersal and pelagic fish	since	1988
Cod; Total stock, SSB and catch at length pr. year-class, recruitment	“	1946
Haddock; -----“-----	“	1946
Capelin; -----“-----	“	1973

2.3 Relevant model tools in fish stock assessment.

Stock assessment models combine information from the fisheries and research surveys to estimate the stock size, the natural mortality and the catch from fisheries. The result forms the basis for management advises on next year quota regulations, but it also produces time-series for use in more basic research such as on stock abundance and recruitment. It is a large international task to gather all the data from the fishing fleet, and there are known to be errors in these data due to reporting errors and illegal dumping of small fish. This has turned a relatively simple problem of “book-keeping” into a quite complex model called Virtual Population Analysis (VPA). The VPA in itself is based on catch statistics and gives estimates for the history of a specific population class (the further back in time the more accurate until a year class is fished out). To estimate present stock abundance, the VPA has to be “tuned” with

other data from recent research surveys which give relative estimates of stock abundance. At present the most commonly used “tuning” techniques are the eXtended Survivors Analysis (XSA) and the Integrated Catch Analysis (ICA). A new stock assessment model (FLEXIBEST) has recently been developed at the Institute of Marine Research. The tuned VPA is used on a single stock, and also on several stocks, which interact by predation and food competition.

None of these rather complex stock assessment models have so far taken environmental information seriously into consideration, and it is at present difficult to fully integrate this type of information into these models. There is still also a great lack of quantitative knowledge on how the environment affects the fish, and therefore it is still premature to do the integration. Consequently, in FJOMP we will investigate the environment-fish relations independent of the general stock assessment models, and aim to deliver results, which can be used as input to the models.

2.4 Ocean Modelling

Hindcast numerical modelling of ocean circulation based on the actual regular observations and climatic fields provides a mean of consistently “homogenising” (in time and space) a wide range of marine physical quantities. Ocean models, based on the state-of-the-art physical understanding of the ocean circulation and their forcing mechanisms, are today capable of reproducing and predicting a wide range of ocean physical parameters to high degree of accuracy. Initiating the models with synoptic fields of meteorological data such as air pressure, wind speed and direction and temperature, the ocean models are capable to reproduce the horizontal and vertical distribution of physical ocean parameters such as currents, temperature, salinity and sea ice distribution and motion. In turn fluxes of momentum, heat etc. and area indices can be calculated. Integration and coupling of these models with other models, e.g. ecosystem models of phytoplankton growth, allows the state and variability of these parameters to be quantified.

3 Definition of Grids to use for the FJOMP database

Most basic EO data are measured as swath data, that is: oriented along satellite orbital track and with the rectangular grid spacing defined by the particular instrument. However the most practical data products to use in FJOMP are temporally averaged over a desired period (day, week, month, etc.) and spatially "binned" into defined rectangular grids of varying definition and size. This is generally done by the suppliers of the EO data in so-called Level-3 products, which are derived parameters averaged and binned in both time and space domain. Such Level-3 EO data will be used for inclusion in the FJOMP project. Some of the commonly used grids are described below.

Sea Surface Temperature data at JPL Pathfinder project (Ch.2.1.2) are available on an equal-angle lat-long grid with increments of a specified size, the grid size being selectable from 360/4096 degree (named "9 km") to 360/720 degree (named "54 km"). Both time averaging and spatial binning of the EO data will be considered in conjunction with the spatial and temporal resolution of the relevant *in situ* and fisheries data as well as model simulations tools to be used. Most likely monthly averaged data will be the basis of the inclusion in the FJOMP database.

Ice concentration data at NSIDC and NERSC (Ch. 2.1.4) are available on a stereographic projection grid with a grid size at the North pole of 25 km.

Altimeter derived data at NERSC (Ch. 2.1.6) are on a UTM projection grid with a spacing along longitude 5°E depending on the satellite track density (26 km for the Topex/Poseidon data).

In-situ data and fish stock data are commonly given as measured values with associated latitude/longitude and time information. They may be mapped onto any convenient spatial grid as well as averaged in time, but are clearly limited by the temporal and spatial resolution of the observations.

The database for FJOMP should use all the above mentioned data sets, as well as others that are found useful, in its Geographical Information System (GIS) Database. For analysing purposes a suitable Common Grid should be defined for use with most of the data sets. For the EO data a grid size of about 25 km using an UTM projection along 5°E will probably be adequate for many of the analyses, however this must be further defined in the main project. Other grid sizes may be defined to cover special finer resolution data, perhaps as associated with special events. Use of an UTM projection centred on 5°E should be suitable for all FJOMP areas, from the fishing grounds west of England to the eastern Barents Sea.

Software for conversion between: 1) the grids used by the various suppliers of data sets to the Database, and 2) the Common Grid (and possible other finer grids needed in FJOMP), should be made available as a toolkit.

4 Statistical Analysis Methods

In the FJOMP context the ocean circulation models (primarily the operational IMR model NORWECOM and the NERSC MICOM model) will be used for description of the temporal and spatial variability of selected physical parameters. In addition quantification of indices and fluxes e.g. through sections, stations or regions similar to those derived from the *in situ* and EO data observations can be produced as outlined further below.

4.1 Definition and Use of Indices

Most ocean EO-data are fairly regular and detailed spatially (km-scale), and also itemporally (daily scale), although optical EO-data often have very large gaps due to clouds. In-situ data and fish-stock data on the contrary, are often very scattered both spatially (along ship positions) and temporally. Still another type of data to consider for the analysis to be done in the FJOMP project is simple time series, defined over a large area as indices. Once defined, the index value may in turn be derived from EO data and/or from in-situ data. Some indices in use in current atmosphere and ocean climate research are listed below.

1) *SO-index*

SO = Southern Oscillation. Index value is the mean Equatorial Pacific Ocean pressure difference, measured between Darwin (Australia) and Tahiti. It is closely correlated with the El-Nino and La-Nina atmosphere and ocean weather patterns in the Pacific (the ENSO pattern), but it also have a smaller correlation with atmosphere and ocean patterns elsewhere.

2) *NAO-index*

This is a measure of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) of the atmosphere (Hurrel, 1995). The NAO-Index value is the mean North Atlantic pressure difference from December to March, measured between Reykjavik and Lisbon. It represents a measure of the dominating weather pattern in and around the North Atlantic, and thus it is also closely correlated with the ocean climate in the areas of interest for FJOMP.

3) *AO-index*

This is a measure of the atmospheric Arctic Oscillation (AO). The index value is the mean Arctic pressure difference, for the winter months, as computed from eigen-value analysis (1.st. principal component). It is a relatively new index (Thompson and Wallace, 1998), made to correlate with the atmosphere patterns in the European Arctic areas, also including some FJOMP areas.

4) *Ice Area index*

This is an area index for Barents Sea Ice Cover (Loeng, 1979). It is used for large-scale description of the Barents Sea ice cover between longitude 25°E and 45°E. Ice covered area south of 76°N is counted negative, while ice free area north of 79°N is counted positive. Values are relative only. This index should be correlated e.g. with the fish stock in the Barents Sea.

5) Other time series

Spatially averaging technique can be used to compute regional time-series from the EO images within defined larger ocean areas. Thus, definition of other indices from the EO parameters (e.g. SST, Sea ice, Eddy kinetic energy, etc.) within selected areas will be made as needed for the investigation.

All time-series and index values will then be compared with each other, and with the trends in fish stock data, using multiple regression analysis and correlation techniques as described in more detail in the next section.

4.2 Analysis Methods

It is believed that the following climate/physical factors, directly or indirectly (through food conditions), are important for fish recruitment, growth and migration:

- Water temperature
- Water turbulence
- Upper ocean layer stability
- Current transport of nutrients, larvae, eggs
- Light conditions for the primary production and visibility for prey and predators.

Since we generally do not have sufficient data coverage (in space and time) for the above parameters, we often have to use other available data sources or model result as an approximation. For instance, the NAO-index (Ch.4.1) may be a measure of Atlantic water inflow, and also the spread of cold polar water into the Nordic Seas. Measured or modelled cloudiness, such as provided by ECMWF, may also be used to approximate the light conditions important for prey/predator interactions and primary production variability. The ocean circulation and its transport may best be obtained through the use of large-scale 3-D numerical models, with e.g. assimilation (input) of current fields and their variability from radar altimeter and *in situ* data.

Parts of the regional climatic variability is coupled to large scale variations such as El Niño. Connection from the Pacific to the Atlantic Ocean occurs mainly through the atmosphere, while connection from e.g. East Greenland to the Norwegian coast may be through direct transport of water masses, which are related to large scale atmospheric conditions. To predict

the variations in the marine climate, it is essential to obtain good quantitative knowledge of the driving mechanisms. Strong links to international climate research efforts (through international projects such as WOCE, JGOFS, GLOBEC, GOOS, CLIVAR and CLIC) are therefore essential.

For the success or failure of recruitment, the environmental conditions during the early life period is critical (the pre-spawning, egg, larvae and 0-group period), and for most of our fish stocks this means most of the year of birth. For rapid growth, the food condition especially during spring and summer is essential. In northern waters this is often strongly related to temperature. The fish migration is believed to be steered by food conditions, temperature distribution, age distribution, and also by unknown factors which leads the fish to their spawning grounds.

To find a combination of the (hopefully few) climatic parameters that are of main importance for a fish stock development, some sort of multiple regression analysis is useful. One form of such analysis to be used is the simple multiple linear regression, which earlier has been used with success on similar tasks. This gives the coefficients a , b , c , and so on, based on the measured or estimated time series in the equation:

$$Biol. Var. = Constant + aClim1 + bClim2 + \dots + cBio1 + dBio2 + \dots$$

where *Biol.Var.* is the independent fisheries variable, *Clim.* is a set of climatic variables and *Bio* a set of biological variables assumed to be important. The Bio variables can, for example, be a measure of the spawning-stock biomass, or the abundance of zooplankton. An example of such results is given in Figure 8 showing the regulation of the North Sea herring 0-group recruitment by the wind climate and the spawning (Svendsen et al., 1995).

The use of this type of correlation analysis will be considered, as well as other types of statistical tools, (e.g. Optimal Interpolation (IO), Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOF)). One requirement is that each time-series should not be auto-correlated. While the auto-correlation is typically found to be weak for many of the time series, this is in general not the case for spawning stocks containing several year-classes. However, knowing that the variability of certain environmental parameters is in general a combined function of several variables, some kind of multivariate analysis is required to estimate the significance of each variable.

HERRING RECRUITMENT

Figure 8: The observed recruitment (*Virtual Population Analysis (VPA)*, defined at page 16) and modelled recruitment of herring for the years 1951 to 1999. The simple statistical model is based on the actual wind records from Utsira (an island off the coast of west Norway) and the Spawning Stock Biomass (SSB) estimated by ICES (after Svendsen et al., 1995).

5 Summary and Recommendations

The importance of the marine living resources to the Norwegian national economy will in decades to come increase significantly. This is due to the fact that the current contribution from the non-renewable oil resources will decrease, as well as the increased demand for higher food production to the growing global population. The role of the fisheries and aquaculture industries will in this respect become more essential and so will the requirements for sustainable development within fisheries research and management. The Norwegian Minister for Fisheries, Peter Angelsen, addressed in a Chronicle in “Bergens Tidende” in January, 2000.

Figure 9: Facsimile of chronicle in Bergens Tidende by the Norwegian Minister of fisheries addressing the future importance of the fisheries and aquaculture industries on the Norwegian economy. For its proper development the focus of R&D is essential to reach the goal. © Bergens Tidende.

The awareness and possible applications of EO based information products are very limited within the traditional fisheries research and management. However, systematic and integrated use of EO data with more traditional records of fisheries statistics is envisaged useful for several applications related to the fisheries. This will require that the present and future records of both satellite EO, relevant fisheries and other marine and oceanographic data are made available over periods of tens of years and aggregated to a level suitable for an efficient and integrated analysis.

Long and extensive EO data records are now, by the Space Agencies or others, systematically processed or pre-processed to a higher level data products and these so called Level-3 data are binned consistently in time and space. Level-3 data products may be well suited for monthly, seasonal, inter-annual or decadal trend analysis in conjunction with other data records obtained at similar time-scales. For shorter duration and less extensive EO data records, these may also be aggregated to an appropriate higher level, however their applications for trend studies are more limited. Still, these shorter time series of EO data have for several applications demonstrated their usefulness. Table 6 summarises the most relevant observation tools (oceanographic, meteorological, model and EO data) and their derived geophysical information that have been identified for use within fisheries research and management.

Observation Tools	Temperature (SST)	Currents	Ocean Biology	Sea Ice	Comments
In situ measurements	•	(•)	•	•	Within the IMR regular monitoring
Numerical Modelling	•	•	(•)	•	Operational physical ocean models
EO Sensor Types					Most Relevant Satellite Sensors
Infra Read	•	(•)	(•)	•	NOAA AVHRR ERS ATSR
Ocean Colour		(•)	•		CZCS SeaWiFS MODIS (2000+) MERIS (2001+)
Radar Altimeter		•			GEOSAT ERS 1 & 2 RA TOPEX/POSEIDON
Passive Microwave				•	NIMBUS 7 DMSP

Table 6: Summary of environmental parameters and their most relevant observational tools, including in situ observations, numerical ocean modelling and EO sensor data, for use within fisheries research and management. Brackets (•) indicate indirect mapping or limited capabilities for FJOMP applications.

Although the implementation of FJOMP will be at a national level it is also necessary to consider and evaluate what kind of activities that already have been initiated in other countries world-wide. In particular countries like USA, Japan, South Africa, Chile and Peru have been active in the use of EO data in support of their fisheries – both for management and commercial catch operations.

Based on the Pilot Study findings and the main Objectives stated in Chapter 1.3 it is suggested to implement a main FJOMP project – “Fisheries Earth Observation and Modelling Project”. The FJOMP project is scheduled for a 18 (used for the proposed schedule) to 24 months duration, pending on the delay of delivery for the various external data sources used. The project is suggested implemented in co-operation between Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) in Bergen.

5.1 Work plan

The following five Work packages are envisaged for completion of the FJOMP main project:

WP1: Development of a FJOMP Database

Design, establish and development of a joint database to facilitate the integrated use and statistical analysis of the *in situ* and EO data sources. The data handling tools to be developed will include means of converting the various sources of data to a common or communicative format for further analysis. The core WP activities will be completed during the first four project months. The task will also include a continuous development and improvement of the database, based on the experience and results achieved through the project applications.

WP 1.1 Implementation of in situ data in database: IMR will make available their fisheries statistics for use in FJOMP. Access information from to other relevant databases, such as from ICES, will be made. Also use of and access to traditional meteorological information will be included.

WP 1.2 Model data: Extraction of relevant fields and parameters from the NORWECOM and MICOM ocean models for use in the project analysis.

WP1.3 Implementation of EO data in database: The level of product aggregation for the various EO sensors are significantly different, hence the approach for the actual processing, reformatting and ingestion will be tailored for each of the EO data sources. The Level-3 AVHRR data products on Sea Surface Temperature (SST) will be easily implemented in the FJOMP database. Processing of Radar Altimeter data to relevant ocean current parameters will be done for data use. Sea ice information from passive microwave data will be included and processing and inclusion of other relevant EO data will be done.

Deliverables: A CD-ROM with the actual project data (level of data aggregation TDB) and a User's Manual.

WP 2: Analysis Tools

Several statistical analysing methods/tools (regression, indices etc.) are in use within both research and fisheries management. Tuning of such routines for handling and use with the project specific data sources and introduction of new routines will be implemented.

Deliverables: Report describing the analysis tools selected used (**TDB**, to be included in WP3 report).

WP 3: Analysis and Interpretations

The extensive sources of data (oceanography, meteorology, fishery, model, EO, etc.) will in an efficient way be processed and analysed in order to identify possible "connections" between the various data sets. The task will include extensive computer processing of data and generation of time series and other statistical variables.

A comprehensive inspection of the regression analysis will be performed in order to identify the most robust relations and correlation existing in the FJOMP database, also including relations between the non-fishery related (geophysical) data sets.

Deliverables: A data report (in digital format, **TBD**) on the main findings of cross-correlation and the statistical analysis, including methods developed in WP2 (**TDB**).

WP 4: Assessment of applications for fisheries research and management

The major outcome of WP 3 will be further investigated in view of their applications for fisheries research and management – linking the marine information derived from EO data sources to fisheries related information. An overall assessment of the benefit and applications of the various parts of the FJOMP database will be done in order to identify and document the potential applications of EO data within fisheries research and management. The conclusions will be ranked according to their possible relevance - as highly useful, potential and not relevant. The most relevant applications will be fully demonstrated and validated versus other information sources.

Deliverables: A report summarising the possible main relations identified, including demonstrations of the best identified applications.

WP 5: Promotion of Results – Future Activities

Based on a possible positive project conclusion, a strategy for a continuation, development, funding and possible future regular use of the FJOMP specific EO information sources within fisheries research and management will be suggested.

Scientific and “popular” publications of the main project results are needed in order to promote a possible future operational use of EO information within fisheries research and management.

Deliverables: A strategy document for a possible continuation and funding of FJOMP related activities. Project marketing folder. Articles in scientific and fisheries management thematic journals. Proceedings from thematic conferences.

5.2 Time Schedule and Milestones

The time schedule as expressed in months from the project start, based on 18 months for implementation, with project start April 1st, 2000.

	Months since April 2000									2001											
WP / Months	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18			
WP 1 Data base	█				█					█											
WP 2 Tools	█		█			█						█									
WP 3 Analysis	█			█						█			█								
WP 4 Assessment	█						█			█			█								
WP 5 Promotion	█									█			█								
Milestones	1									MtR			2			3			4		

Major Milestones:

1. First version of FJOM database (month 4).

MtR: Mid-term Review of project progress.

2. Data report, including method descriptions, on the findings of the statistical analysis and the identified useful correlation within the database.
3. Final version of the FJOMP database, including its documentation. Report presenting the possible identified applications including EO data of relevance to the fisheries research and management.
4. Project completion. A strategy document for a possible continuation of FJOMP applications. Project marketing material. Submitted publications and proceedings.

5.3 Budget

Based on the Work packages described above the following budget is estimated. The estimates are based on standard public accepted on hourly rates (1.6 % of annual salary) for scientific projects.

Workpackage	NERSC	IMR	Total
WP 1	270000	200000	470000
WP 2	90000	90000	180000
WP 3	250000	200000	450000
WP 4	90000	150000	240000
WP 5	90000	90000	180000
Data repro. costs	30000	20000	50000
Computer time	30000	20000	50000
Other costs, travel	100000	80000	180000
Total	950000	850000	1800000

Revised project budget, omitting WP 5 and NOK 120.000 of the project travel budget:

Workpackage	NERSC	IMR	Total
WP 1	330000	240000	570000
WP 2	100000	90000	190000
WP 3	270000	220000	490000
WP 4	100000	150000	250000
WP 5	0	0	0
Total	800000	700000	1500000

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